

Insight #2.

Conducting an OMC in the INTERCEPT Project: Engaging the Market for Remote Vehicle Stopping Solutions

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1. About us

Polish Platform for Homeland Security (PPHS), Corvers Procurement Services BV and CORVERS Greece Monoprosopi I.K.E. (collaboratively CORVERS), Kentro Meleton Asfaleias (KEMEA), and DIGINNOV-Digital Innovation Consulting S.R.L. (DIGINNOV) bring together their expertise to drive the success of the INTERCEPT project. PPHS coordinates the project, leveraging its strong connections with European security practitioners and stakeholders. KEMEA contributes experience in cross-border collaborations in innovation procurement, acting as Lead Procurer, coordinating the User Observatory Group (UOG) and the Group of Public Buyers, and defining the overall procurement strategy. DIGINNOV provides cutting-edge knowledge in technology evaluation, innovation needs, and security applications, ensuring alignment with user requirements and strategic goals. CORVERS specialises in innovation procurement and legal frameworks, providing expert guidance on Pre-Commercial Procurement (PCP) preparation and training for public buyers.

2. Executive summary

Open Market Consultations (OMCs) are a strategic and legally grounded instrument in the European Union's innovation procurement framework. They allow public buyers to engage with the market before launching a tender, to assess the maturity of potential solutions, validate assumptions regarding technical and legal feasibility, and ensure future procurements are transparent, competitive, and proportionate. Rooted in EU public procurement law, OMCs provide a structured, non-discriminatory method to align demand and supply in pre-commercial and innovative procurement contexts, including Pre-Commercial Procurement (PCP) and Public Procurement of Innovative Solutions (PPI).

This insight explores both the **legal basis and practical implementation of OMCs**, with a focus on their procedural safeguards, strategic utility, and role in preparing demand-driven innovation procurements. Drawing on the European Assistance for Innovation Procurement (EAFIP) Toolkit and relevant EU case law, the insight highlights how OMCs must comply with principles of equal treatment, non-discrimination, transparency, and proportionality, while ensuring that competition is not distorted or precluded and protecting commercially sensitive information.

This insight also examines the specific application of this methodology in the **INTERCEPT project**, a Horizon Europe Coordination and Support Action (CSA) preparing the ground for a potential cross-border PCP in Remote Vehicle Stopping (RVS) technologies for Law Enforcement Authorities (LEAs). Starting with the publication of a Prior Information Notice (PIN), followed by a detailed OMC document, targeted Request for Information (RFI) questionnaires, multilingual webinars, e-pitching sessions and a central hybrid event in Warsaw, INTERCEPT's OMC serves as a model for responsible and inclusive pre-procurement engagement. Preliminary findings suggest strong market interest but also legal and operational gaps that support the case for a structured innovation procurement. The final OMC report, published on 18 July 2025, provided further guidance for the next steps in PCP planning.

3. Introduction: scope & objectives of INTERCEPT

In recent decades, the European Union has witnessed a growing number of security threats involving motor vehicles — from high-speed police chases and vehicle theft to deliberate vehicle-ramming attacks and terrorism-related incidents. These threats, often executed with alarming ease and speed, have underlined the urgent need for innovative tools that can help LEAs mitigate the risks posed by vehicles used as instruments of harm.

Motor vehicles continue to be exploited in a wide range of unlawful acts, including driving under the influence (DUI) offences, theft, violent crime, and targeted attacks. The combination of increasing frequency and rising operational complexity of such threats has outpaced the capabilities of existing technologies, calling for coordinated and technologically advanced responses at the EU level.

Traffic-related operations remain among the most hazardous duties for law enforcement officers. High-speed pursuits and roadside interventions frequently result in life-threatening outcomes. Data from France in 2019, for example, recorded over 22,000 police pursuits, which led to 5,789 accidents and 260 fatalities. Notably, 91% of these pursuits stemmed from non-violent offences, emphasising the disproportionate risks involved. Similar patterns are evident across other Member States, with stolen vehicles and DUI-related incidents continuing to challenge law enforcement and strain public safety systems.

The threat posed by vehicles has also taken a more insidious form in recent years: deliberate vehicle-ramming attacks. These tactics — characterised by the intentional use of vehicles to breach secured perimeters or cause mass casualties — are attractive to perpetrators due to their simplicity, low resource requirement, and high-impact potential. They have been deployed in terrorist plots, psychiatric crises, and opportunistic criminal acts. Attackers have, in some instances, used vehicles to gain access to sensitive sites before deploying further weapons or explosives, compounding the security risk.

Despite advances in commercial vehicle safety features — including collision avoidance systems and emergency braking — existing technologies do not seem to be designed to serve law enforcement needs in high-risk, real-time intervention scenarios. There remains a capability gap: no universal, scalable, and remotely operable solution currently exists to safely and effectively stop a moving vehicle without endangering lives or compromising property.

To bridge this gap, the INTERCEPT project was launched, co-funded by the European Union, to lay the groundwork for a potential **Pre-Commercial Procurement (PCP)**. Rather than directly procuring solutions, INTERCEPT aims to define and validate the operational, technical, legal, and ethical framework necessary for a future PCP targeting RVS technologies. The project brings together a consortium of practitioners, procurement experts, legal advisors, and technology analysts to engage with the market, end users, and policy stakeholders in a structured, strategic process.

The need for such a project was confirmed during consultations within the i-LEAD project. In February 2023, representatives of LEAs, procurement professionals, and subject matter experts collectively noted the absence of a universal, reliable, and lawful RVS solution. Their findings helped solidify the case for deeper market exploration and structured preparation, underlining the importance of aligning any future procurement with both user needs and legal constraints across the EU.

A central instrument in this preparatory phase is the **Open Market Consultation (OMC)**. The OMC allows INTERCEPT to engage with potential suppliers, researchers, and end users to assess the state of the art, identify promising technologies, and test the viability of proposed use cases. It is also essential for mapping the innovation landscape, detecting legal or ethical challenges, and refining the functional and performance requirements that would later shape a PCP.

The project's broader objectives include enhancing cross-border cooperation among public buyers, promoting responsible innovation, and improving the overall readiness of public procurement systems to address emerging security challenges.

4. OMC in the context of INTERCEPT

The INTERCEPT project, a Horizon Europe Coordination and Support Action (CSA), aims to prepare the legal, technical, and strategic ground for a potential joint cross-border Pre-Commercial Procurement (PCP) in the field of RVS technologies for Law Enforcement Authorities (LEAs). In this preparatory context, the conduct of an OMC represents an important phase that combines legal compliance with substantive market intelligence gathering.

Within this context, the OMC plays an essential role. It serves not only as a structured engagement process with the market, but also as a means of verifying **whether the identified needs are genuinely unmet, whether the market is capable of addressing them, and whether further Research and Development (R&D) is still necessary**. The OMC supports strategic alignment between public sector demand and innovation supply and ensures that any future procurement is informed, realistic, and inclusive.

The figure below illustrates how the OMC fits into the broader structure of the INTERCEPT project and how it contributes to downstream procurement planning:

Figure 1: The methodology of the Intercept project.

As shown in the figure, the INTERCEPT lifecycle begins with **Phase 0 – the Preparatory Stage**, during which **the project consortium conducts extensive groundwork: identifying operational gaps and needs, collecting requirements, benchmarking candidate technologies, conducting a State-of-the-Art (SOTA) analysis, and carrying out the OMC**. The insights gained through the OMC directly inform the common challenge, allowing end-users to collectively validate which functional and technical requirements should be addressed in a future procurement.

The OMC also bridges the gap between initial assessments and later procedural planning. It supports the development of a Joint Procurement Agreement among the group of public buyers and feeds into the legal and technical documentation required for any potential PCP call for tenders. Should the consortium determine that the identified needs cannot yet be met by commercially available solutions and that further research and development are required, the process may transition into a multi-phase PCP, involving competitive selection, solution design, prototype development, and final operational validation.

4.1. What is an Open Market Consultation (OMC)?

An Open Market Consultation is an open dialogue between procurer(s) and the market, in which the procurers ask for the view of the market to identify the ability thereof to meet the needs of the procurer(s).¹ Under EU law, the OMC is grounded primarily in the 2014 EU Public Procurement Directives:

- Article 40 of the Public Sector Directive 2014/24/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 26 February 2014 on public procurement and article 58 of Directive 2014/25/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 26 February 2014 on procurement by entities operating in the water, energy, transport and postal services sectors provide that **“Before launching a procurement procedure, contracting authorities may conduct market consultations with a view to preparing the procurement and informing**

¹ European Commission, <https://projects.research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/en/node/11962#:~:text=An%20open%20market%20consultation%20is%20an%20open%20dialogue,to%20meet%20the%20needs%20of%20the%20procurer%20%28s%29.>

economic operators of their procurement plans and requirements. For this purpose, contracting authorities may, for example, seek or accept advice from independent experts or authorities or from market participants. That advice may be used in the planning and conduct of the procurement procedure, provided that such advice does not have the effect of distorting competition and does not result in a violation of the principles of non-discrimination and transparency.”;

- Furthermore, article 41 of the Public Sector Directive and, respectively, article 59 of the Utilities Directive complete the general provisions aforementioned and provide the rules for the prior involvement of candidates and tenderers: “*Where a candidate or tenderer or an undertaking related to a candidate or tenderer has advised the contracting authority, whether in the context of Article 40 / 58 (market consultation) or not, or has otherwise been involved in the preparation of the procurement procedure, **the contracting authority shall take appropriate measures to ensure that competition is not distorted by the participation of that candidate or tenderer.***”

These provisions apply regardless of whether the procurer later conducts a PCP (outside the scope of the Directives) or a PPI (subject to them). For example, the **Horizon Europe Work Programme 2023–2025 General Annexes** specify that to prepare the call for tender, an open market consultation with potential tenderers and end-users must be held to broach the views of the market on the intended scope of the R&D. They permit the market consultation to address not only tender specifications but any element relevant to procurement planning — including technological feasibility, procedural choices, selection criteria, IPR arrangements, and budget or timing constraints.

The **CJEU has further clarified** in the *Stadt Halle* case (C-26/03) and the *Fabricom* case (C-21/03) that preparatory acts which do not directly impact the selection of an economic operator are not subject to review under public procurement law. However, contracting authorities must exercise vigilance to ensure that such consultations do not result in unlawful preferential treatment.

The OMC supports strategic alignment between public sector demand and innovation supply and ensures that any future procurement is informed, realistic, and inclusive. Importantly, it is conducted in accordance with the **fundamental principles of EU public procurement law** as derived from the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU): **equal treatment, non-discrimination, transparency, and proportionality**. These principles safeguard the integrity of the consultation process and ensure a fair and competitive basis for any subsequent procurement.

From a competition law perspective, the consultation must also comply with **Article 101 TFEU** (prohibition of anti-competitive agreements), requiring that no commercially sensitive or individual business strategy information be improperly disclosed among competitors during the consultation process. Measures such as anonymised reporting, the publication of general findings (FAQs), and a firewall between confidential and shared data are mandated under best practice standards.

4.2. The importance of an OMC for INTERCEPT

The OMC conducted under the INTERCEPT project serves several legally and strategically important purposes. In general, the objectives of an OMC are to validate the findings of the market and State-of-the-Art (SOTA) analysis, assess the viability of the envisaged technical and financial provisions, and raise awareness among market stakeholders of the upcoming innovation procurement. It also provides a structured opportunity to collect informed feedback from both technology providers and end users, which can then be used to refine tender specifications and procurement strategies.

The OMC aims, on the one hand, to inform technology vendors regarding the potential future PCP and, on the other hand, to understand their capabilities to satisfy the procurers' needs and to obtain their input on the viability of the procurement plans and conditions as described in the OMC document and annexes.

In sum, the objectives of this OMC activities are to:

1. Validate the findings of the SOTA analysis and the viability of the set of technical and financial provisions.
2. Raise awareness of the industry and relevant stakeholders regarding the upcoming PCP.

3. Collect insights from the industry and relevant stakeholders (including users) to fine-tune the tender specifications.

The OMC enables the consortium to assess whether the technological solutions needed to stop motor vehicles remotely are already commercially available or whether they still require further research and development. This distinction is essential, as it determines whether a future public procurement process would be geared toward existing innovations or would need to stimulate the market to develop entirely new ones.

4.3. Key activities of the INTERCEPT OMC

The INTERCEPT OMC was structured in accordance with best practices, including the use of early PIN publication and multilingual outreach, in order to engage a wide range of technology providers, public buyers, end-users, and other interested actors. The figure below outlines the main activities carried out to date.

Figure 2: The milestones of the Intercept OMC activities.

1. Prior Information Notice (PIN) Publication

On 3 March 2025, a PIN was published in the Tenders Electronic Daily (TED) platform, the official EU procurement portal. The PIN formally announced the OMC and alerted market participants across the EU of the project's intention to explore innovation procurement in the area of remote vehicle-stopping solutions.

The PIN outlined the scope of the consultation, defined its non-binding nature, and signalled the Consortium's intent to gather input on technical feasibility, legal considerations, and innovation potential. It also served to ensure compliance with transparency obligations and gave sufficient advance notice to interested parties.

OPEN MARKET CONSULTATIONS

The **Open Market Consultations (OMC)** and e-pitching sessions will be organised to communicate procurers' needs to the market well in advance, cross-check the findings of the state-of-the-art analysis and obtain relevant information from suppliers on existing (or to be developed) technologies. These events will also help the consortium to validate the technical and financial provisions of a future Pre-Commercial Procurement.

The scope of the OMC is to raise awareness in the industry regarding the upcoming tender to be launched and to collect insights on industry skills, which can be used to fine-tune the tender specifications.

The INTERCEPT team has prepared a document that includes all the information about the planned OMC. To learn more, [open the OMC document using this link](#).

OMC TIMELINE

- ✓ The central onsite and online event in Warsaw, 25 June
- ✓ National webinars:
 - In Spanish, 9 May 10:00 – 12:00 CET
 - In English, 12 May 10:00 – 12:00 CET
 - In French, 13 May 10:00 – 12:00 CET
 - In Finnish, 13 May 12:30 – 14:30 EET
 - In Italian, 14 May 12:30 – 14:30 CET
 - In Polish, 15 May 10:00 – 12:00 CEST
 - In Slovak, 15 May 12:30 – 14:30 CET
 - In Greek, 22 May 11:00 – 13:00 EET

Figure 3: OMC page of the Intercept's website.

2. Publication of the OMC Document

To complement the PIN, a detailed OMC document was made available on the INTERCEPT project website. This document introduced the background and objectives of INTERCEPT, outlined the scope of the future PCP, and provided a detailed explanation of six operational use cases, including urban high-speed pursuits, vehicle

ramming incidents, and scenarios involving motorcycles or distressed drivers. The document also elaborated on the functional, technical, legal, and ethical requirements derived from end-user needs. Importantly, it clarified the voluntary and non-competitive nature of the OMC, and the expectations for participation. It invited stakeholders to reflect on the state of the art, provide feedback on the relevance of the identified needs, and highlight any gaps or constraints.

Figure 4: Excerpts from the OMC document.

3. RFI Questionnaires

INTERCEPT issued two Requests for Information (RFIs) questionnaires through the EU Survey platform—one for technology providers and one for end-users. The RFI for technology providers explored several dimensions: company profiles, TRLs of relevant solutions, key performance features such as tracking or neutralisation capabilities, safety mechanisms, IPR status, legal limitations, and budget/time estimates for each use case. The RFI for end users gathered insight into the operational relevance of the proposed use cases, technical expectations, communication and integration

requirements, legal or ethical limitations, and interest in future piloting or testing. Together, these surveys provided a rich evidence base from both the supply and demand perspectives.

INTERCEPT

Request for Information Questionnaire for End Users

INTERCEPT: Innovation Procurement of Advanced Technologies for Safe Remote Vehicle Stopping by Law Enforcement

This survey is part of the Open Market Consultation (OMC) of the INTERCEPT project. It should provide the INTERCEPT Consortium with feedback from the market about the challenge concerning enhancing the capabilities of European law enforcement authorities and provide them with information about effective means to safely stop vehicles remotely. The OMC document, to which this questionnaire is an annex, can be found on the project's website (<https://intercept-horizon.eu>).

End users are invited to answer all the questions in this survey (one survey per company). The results will be considered when drafting the tender documents for the future PCP. The deadline to submit your response is **23 May 2025**. In case further input is needed, a deadline extension may be announced on the INTERCEPT project website.

Please note that taking part in this survey is not a prerequisite for participation in the future PCP and does not give any advantage to any end user. INTERCEPT will ensure transparency, openness, and equal treatment of all economic operators. All information provided in the questionnaire will be anonymised, summarised and published online in English on the project's website.

Your personal data will be collected, processed, stored, and used by the INTERCEPT consortium with the sole purpose of gathering information from the market within the framework of the INTERCEPT project. Personal data will be treated as strictly confidential according to the General Data Protection Regulation (Regulation 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council - GDPR). You may exercise your right to access your personal data and the right to rectify such data by contacting: contact@intercept-horizon.eu.

GENERAL INFORMATION

Figure 5: RFI for End Users

INTERCEPT

Request for Information Questionnaire for Technology Providers

INTERCEPT: Innovation Procurement of Advanced Technologies for Safe Remote Vehicle Stopping by Law Enforcement

This survey is part of the Open Market Consultation (OMC) of the INTERCEPT project. It should provide the INTERCEPT Consortium with feedback from the market about the challenge concerning enhancing the capabilities of European law enforcement authorities and provide them with information about effective means to safely stop vehicles remotely. The OMC document, to which this questionnaire is an annex, can be found on the project's website (<https://intercept-horizon.eu>).

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GENERAL INFORMATION

Figure 6: RFI for Technology Providers

4. OMC Webinars in Multiple EU Languages

To enhance accessibility, INTERCEPT organised multiple webinars between 9–15 May 2025 in different official EU languages, including English, French, Spanish and Slovak. These sessions introduced participants to the INTERCEPT project, the PCP model, the scope of the use cases, and the objectives of the OMC. Presenters from the consortium explained the procurement strategy, outlined the findings from the State-of-the-Art and IPR analyses, and responded to questions from participants. All webinars were recorded and published online to ensure that all interested stakeholders could access the same information, in line with transparency and equal treatment principles.

Figure 7: Intercept's YouTube page including OMC webinar recordings.

5. Preliminary Findings Published

The preliminary results of the OMC activities were published in a consolidated report on 30 May 2025. This interim document summarised anonymised input received through the RFIs and webinars. It provided an overview of technological readiness, perceived implementation barriers, legal and ethical considerations, and innovation gaps. The report identified trends in supplier responses, including the use of radio frequency (RF)-based engine neutralisation, unmanned aerial vehicles (UAV) surveillance and tracking, AI-driven behaviour detection, and mechanical interception systems. It also reflected end users' prioritisation of public safety, real-time control, and the need for solutions that minimise disruption and align with legal frameworks. This report served as a feedback tool ahead of the main OMC event and allowed vendors to better align their contributions. It also provided an updated list and description of the security use cases, which were refined from six to three.

<p>4. Summary of the replies to the RFI questionnaire</p> <p>The Request for Information surveys are part of the OMC of the INTERCEPT project. Two surveys were created, including the targeted questions for technology providers and end users.</p> <p>The RFI questionnaire collected input from technology providers on solutions for the remote and safe stopping of vehicles. It focused on company profiles, existing or emerging technologies, and their suitability for six predefined high-risk use cases. Providers were asked to describe key technical features, safety mechanisms, development timelines, and readiness levels. The questionnaire also explored innovation compared to the current state-of-the-art, use of patents or standards, and any technical or operational barriers. Additional input on risks and support needed for development was also requested.</p> <p>On the other hand, the RFI questionnaire for end users aimed to understand operational needs, technical expectations, and legal considerations related to remote vehicle-stopping solutions. Respondents were asked to share organisational details, the frequency and context of high-risk incidents, and rank the relevance of the six INTERCEPT use cases. Input was gathered on current tools, critical technical requirements, preferred environments for testing, and integration needs. The questionnaire also explored legal, ethical, and societal concerns, as well as end users' willingness to engage in testing, certification needs, and procurement constraints.</p> <p>The (preliminary) results summarised below will be considered when drafting the tender documents for the future PCP.</p> <p>After completing the analysis of the responses, the INTERCEPT Consortium will publish a final OMC report, scheduled for release on 4 July 2024. The purpose of this report is to inform the market and relevant stakeholders ahead of the upcoming e-pitching events and to support transparent, broad-based information exchange. All responses received through the EU Survey have been fully anonymised. As such, the report will present only aggregated findings and summarised insights derived from the collected data. The final OMC report will be made publicly available on the official INTERCEPT project website.</p>	<p>5. Conclusions</p> <p>The INTERCEPT OMC engaged both end users and technology providers across Europe to gather insights into current operational challenges and the technological landscape related to remote vehicle-stopping solutions. The consultation attracted contributions from public security authorities and private sector innovators, providing a diverse and informative view of needs, capabilities, and constraints.</p> <p>End users emphasised that high-risk vehicle incidents occur frequently, particularly in urban environments. Among the six proposed use cases, scenarios involving high-speed pursuits and vehicle ramming attacks were deemed most relevant. Respondents noted that current intervention tools are largely absent or limited to pursuit contexts, highlighting a significant operational gap. Effectiveness, response time, and minimal public disruption were ranked as the top priorities for any future solution. Legal, ethical, and public trust considerations—especially relating to surveillance, proportionality, and safety—were also identified as essential factors to address in system development and deployment.</p> <p>Technology providers reported a variety of innovative solutions in progress or under development, including adhesive-based tracking devices, autonomous UAV systems, remote RF-based engine disablement tools, and integrated perception and control platforms. Most providers confirmed awareness of existing technological options but noted considerable room for advancement beyond the current state of the art. Key areas of innovation include AI-driven behaviour prediction, GNSS-independent tracking, secure communication in complex environments, and miniaturisation of intervention technologies. Providers also cited practical challenges such as system reliability in diverse conditions, legal authorisations for use, and the need for standardisation across different vehicle types and deployment scenarios.</p> <p>There was a broad consensus among participants on the importance of interoperability, user control flexibility and compliance with data protection and national regulations. While several providers expressed readiness to participate in prototyping and validation, others noted that further clarifications on technical</p>
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Figure 8: Excerpts from the preliminary OMC report.

6. E-Pitching Sessions

To facilitate direct dialogue, INTERCEPT organised e-pitching sessions on 3–4 June 2025. These confidential online meetings gave selected technology providers the opportunity to present their preliminary ideas to members of the consortium and public buyers. Each session was structured around a common presentation template and included discussion time for clarification. Suppliers demonstrated how their solutions addressed one or more use cases, explained technical features, and reflected on development timelines and integration pathways. These engagements helped assess feasibility, gauge innovation maturity, and better understand individual supplier capabilities.

E-PITCHING SESSIONS

During the **e-pitching sessions**, the market suppliers will have the opportunity to present how their existing solutions could tackle the selected procurement challenges. Each technology provider will have a slot dedicated to present their solutions and explain how they can address the challenge. The e-pitching sessions will consist of online events. Each technology provider can participate in more than one session.

TIMELINE

- 1st E-pitching session, 3 June 10:00 – 13:00 CEST
- 2nd E-pitching session, 4 June 10:00 – 13:00 CEST
- 3rd E-pitching session, 5 June 10:00 – 13:00 CEST

Figure 9: Intercept's e-pitching sessions page.

7. Main OMC Event in Warsaw

The OMC served as a structured dialogue through which public procurers sought insights from the market to assess its capacity to meet identified needs. This engagement helped bridge the gap between the public sector (demand side) and technology providers (supply side), ensuring alignment between procurement objectives and market capabilities.

During the event, the procurers presented their findings from the prior-art and IPR analyses, the standards landscape, contractual frameworks, and project feasibility studies. Technology providers were invited to contribute insights on structuring the procurement phases, resource planning, and identifying and mitigating key risks. The event also focused on validating operational needs, exploring relevant technologies, and assessing innovation potential and readiness levels.

Moreover, the OMC provided a platform for dialogue on future collaboration opportunities, including the formation of consortia and mechanisms to enhance participation, particularly by small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). These

discussions were intended to inform and refine the tender preparation process and support the co-development of effective, innovative solutions.

As part of the broader OMC process, a dedicated workshop was also conducted to validate preliminary findings related to the three identified Use Cases. This workshop examined technological readiness and procurement feasibility within the context of each Use Case.

The objective of the consultation was to collect expert input from industry stakeholders and technology providers on two critical dimensions of the forthcoming Pre-Commercial Procurement: the structuring and phasing of the project and its associated budget allocation, and the current status and future potential of relevant technological innovations.

Taken together, these activities reflect INTERCEPT's commitment to responsible innovation procurement preparation. The OMC process helped ensure that any future PCP will be grounded in real-world needs, shaped by market intelligence, and

designed in compliance with the core principles of fairness, openness, and proportionality.

4.4. Insights and observations from the market

The results of the INTERCEPT OMC revealed a diverse innovation ecosystem, with active participation from both technology providers and public authorities. These findings provided insight into the current state of the market, the maturity and direction of relevant technologies, and the broader legal, operational, and ethical constraints that will shape a potential future procurement.

The response to the technology providers' questionnaire indicated that the market is active, innovative, but fragmented. Respondents included start-ups, SMEs from across Europe, working in domains ranging from radio frequency (RF) technologies, UAV and drone systems, artificial intelligence, and sensor fusion, to mechanical interception solutions. Most of the technologies proposed by suppliers fall between TRLs 5 and 7. This suggests that while promising building blocks exist, fully integrated, deployable RVS systems are not yet commercially available—supporting the case for a PCP. Some suppliers proposed combinations of capabilities, such as tracking and neutralisation, rather than end-to-end solutions covering detection, classification, pursuit, control, and stoppage in a single architecture.

The responses also demonstrated significant heterogeneity in approaches. Several suppliers proposed RF-based neutralisation techniques, either targeting the vehicle's electronic systems or disrupting control signals. Others focused on detection and localisation via advanced imaging, LIDAR, or acoustic sensors, while a smaller subset presented emerging AI-driven behavioural prediction tools that could support early identification of vehicular threats. Despite this diversity, respondents expressed a shared understanding of the operational and legal challenges involved. Notably, concerns were raised about electromagnetic spectrum licensing, GDPR compliance for tracking technologies, interoperability with existing LEA systems, and public perception of intrusive or forceful intervention technologies.

From the demand side, the end-users' questionnaire responses confirmed that the six use cases developed by INTERCEPT are indeed operationally relevant across a broad

spectrum of law enforcement agencies in Europe. Respondents consistently identified urban high-speed pursuits, vehicle ramming threats, and incidents involving vulnerable populations (such as minors or psychologically distressed drivers) as high-priority scenarios. Interestingly, while most LEAs reported encountering such events regularly, few indicated that they currently have access to effective tools to deal with them. Current methods often rely on high-risk tactics such as physical barriers, ramming, or manual interception—posing dangers to officers, suspects, and bystanders alike.

LEAs participating in the RFI also highlighted the need for technologies that allow for **proportional, selective, and remotely operable interventions**. Requirements such as fast response times, operator control, minimal collateral damage, and the ability to function in dense urban or GNSS-denied environments were repeatedly emphasised. Integration with existing communication and command systems was another recurring theme, particularly the need for seamless inclusion in standard radio or vehicle networks already deployed across Member States. Importantly, some organisations expressed a willingness to participate in field testing, pilot deployments, and technical validation, provided that legal frameworks, liability considerations, and public accountability mechanisms are defined.

The e-pitching sessions offered additional insights into the maturity and direction of proposed solutions. Participating suppliers presented their approaches to one or more use cases, outlined expected performance, and discussed development timelines and integration challenges. While the format did not facilitate direct interaction among suppliers, it enabled a deeper technical and legal dialogue with the consortium, reinforcing the need for regulatory clarity and coordination in future procurement planning.

The hybrid OMC event held in Warsaw on 25–26 June 2025 further confirmed and expanded these findings. During the event, stakeholders from across Europe exchanged perspectives on the use cases, assessed the practicality of different technological paths, and identified potential regulatory bottlenecks. In-depth discussions addressed issues such as public acceptance, legal proportionality, and the interoperability of proposed solutions. The event helped align procurement objectives

with real-world operational constraints and contributed to refining the project's innovation roadmap.

Across both groups of respondents, one notable observation was the clear demand for **interoperability, legal clarity, and public trust**. Technology providers want to innovate but need confidence that their solutions will be legally permissible and publicly accepted. Law enforcement agencies are eager to adopt safer intervention tools, but not at the cost of triggering political, legal, or reputational risks. This convergence around the importance of responsible innovation highlights the strategic value of the INTERCEPT project: it does not only identify the technological frontier but also helps define the legal and ethical boundaries within which a European innovation procurement must operate.

The final OMC report, published on 18 July 2025, consolidates the insights gathered from RFIs, e-pitching sessions, webinars, and the Warsaw event, offering comprehensive findings to guide the next steps in procurement planning.

5. Conclusions

OMCs are an essential preparatory tool in the European Union's innovation procurement landscape, especially in fields that involve emerging technologies, complex stakeholder ecosystems, and sensitive public interest objectives. Legally grounded in the 2014 EU Public Procurement Directives and developed in line with Treaty principles of transparency, equal treatment, non-discrimination, and proportionality, the OMC serves a dual function: to reduce information asymmetries between public buyers and the market, and to validate the legal and technical feasibility of a proposed procurement approach—particularly in contexts requiring pre-commercial or innovative solutions.

Within this framework, the OMC conducted under the INTERCEPT project has exemplified the value of this mechanism in a real-world, high-stakes public security context. INTERCEPT has used the OMC not only to assess market capabilities in the area of RVS technologies but also to foster trust and alignment between public authorities and technology suppliers. By combining structured documentation, multilingual engagement tools, targeted RFIs, legal safeguards, thematic analysis, confidential e-pitching sessions, and a multi-stakeholder hybrid event, the project has operationalised the principles of responsible innovation procurement across borders.

The final results of the INTERCEPT OMC suggest that no commercially available, fully compliant RVS solution currently meets the operational, legal, and safety criteria identified by European law enforcement agencies. At the same time, the market landscape is dynamic and receptive, with multiple promising components at TRL 5–7 already in development. This confirms the relevance of a future PCP and underscores the importance of sustained dialogue, legal clarity, and strategic coordination in shaping the next steps.

In conclusion, the INTERCEPT OMC reinforces the role of early and transparent engagement with the market. The final OMC report, published on the 18th of July 2025, consolidates these insights.